

PRODUCTION TI-TA25 (HTSMAS) USING ROLLING PROCESS: OXIDATION BEHAVIOUR AND ITS IMPACT ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE EVOLUTION AND TEMPERATURES OF TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT: *There are many works on developing advanced shape memory alloys with unique properties unmatched by conventional shape memory alloys. Unlike conventional shape memory alloys, which exhibit martensitic transformation start temperatures below 100°C, HTSMAs exhibit martensitic transformation start temperatures above 100°C. Here, we investigate the transformation behavior and microstructure of Ti-Ta25 HTSMAs before and after oxidation using the thermogravimetric analysis TGA in the range from 25°C - 1000°C. Microstructural investigations using transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), optical microscopy (OM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were studied and combined with DTA/TGA before oxidation. After oxidation, TGA, in combination with microstructural investigations using TEM, focused ion beam (FIP), and DTA, were used to study the oxide scale formed on the surface of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMAs. Before oxidation, two different phases could be seen, β - phase and α - phase. After oxidation, two stages of oxidation were found: linear oxidation gain during the early stage of oxidation, until 600°C, followed by a parabolic oxidation gain at higher temperatures. Three different phases could be seen: β - phase, α - phase, and ω - phase. TEM analysis of oxide film demonstrated the presence of oxide scale of Ta₂O₅ and TiO₂. Results show a decomposition into the Ti-rich α -phase, Ta-rich phase, and weak precipitation of the ω - phase associated with the formation of Ti - oxide and Ta -oxide leads to an instantaneous loss of martensitic transformation of Ti-Ta25 HTSMAs.*

KEYWORDS: *High-temperature shape memory alloys; Cold Rolling; Oxides Scale; Ti-Ta alloys; Functional degradation; Oxidation; TiO₂; Martensitic Transformation*

1 INTRODUCTION

There is growing scientific and industrial interest in the development of shape memory alloys (SMAs) capable of operating at elevated temperatures (Radhi et al., 2020), particularly those exhibiting phase transformation temperatures exceeding 100 °C, commonly referred to as high-temperature shape memory alloys (HTSMAs) (Sam, 2018). Despite their promising functional characteristics, the current industrial utilization of HTSMAs re-mains confined to niche applications, primarily due to material and processing limitations (Bourke, 2024). Most HTSMAs are derived from the nick-el-titanium (Ni-Ti) system (Mohammed & Al-khafaji, 2023; Radhi & Al-Khafaji, 2018; Shahee et al., 2024), wherein the transformation temper-ature is elevated through the incorporation of ter-nary alloying elements such as

platinum (Pt), palladium (Pd) and hafnium (Hf) (Li et al., 2021). While these alloying strategies effectively raise transformation thresholds, they are often con-strained by the economic burden of using costly noble metals or the resultant material workability degradation. However, recent advancements have demonstrated that in the case of Ni-Ti-Hf-based HTSMAs, the workability challenges can be miti-gated through optimized thermomechanical pro-cessing routes, thereby enabling the fabrication of thin wire geometries and expanding their potential for practical implementation (Wires, 2022).

Ti - Ta-based alloys that exhibit transformation temperatures above 100 °C have much potential for usage as high-temperature shape memory. The early works about Ti - Ta HTSMAs were reported by Buenconsejo et al. (Buenconsejo, Kim, Hosoda, et

al., 2009). They reported that the Ti–Ta system with 30 – 40 at% tantalum can exhibit martensitic transformation between β - phase with BCC structure and α'' - phase with orthorhombic structure. In addition, Buenconsejo et al. reported that Ti – Ta HTSMAs ω – phase with hexagonal structure can occur in the temperatures regime between 100 °C and 400 °C. Thus, the transformation between β – phase and α'' - the ω – phase formation governs phase. However, ω – phase stabilizes β – phase (Miyazaki et al., 2009).

Many studies were carried out on suppressing the ω – phase (Miyazaki et al., 2009; Zheng et al., 2012). Alloying with ternary elements Al or Sn has been reported to delay the formation of ω – phase (Buenconsejo, Kim, & Miyazaki, 2009). Among the studies that attempt to suppress ω – phase is a publication by Niendorf et al. (Niendorf et al., 2014, 2015). The authors reported that the ω – phase can be dissolved with a short heat treatment using annealing heat treatment at 600 °C.

Previous studies have reported the oxidation behavior of Ti–Ta in high temperatures above 800 °C with 0 – 30 at% tantalum (Chen & Rosa, 1980; Hanrahan & Butt, 1997; Prokoshkin et al., 1984). Recently, Dennis et al. investigated the impact of oxidation on transformation temperatures of Ti – Ta30 HTSMAs at temperature regimes from 330 °C in the air to 850 °C (Langenkämper et al., 2019). In addition, it was demonstrated early that the composition of Ti – Ta HTSMAs has a significant effect on the martensitic transformation temperatures (Chakraborty et al., 2017; Chilnicean et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2014), which led to further investigation by Maier et al. (Maier et al., 2017); they investigated the microstructural of Ti–Ta HTSMAs up on mechanical load with low tantalum content 25at%. Thus, this research aims to investigate the oxidation behavior and its consequent influence on the microstructural evolution and martensitic transformation temperatures of Ti–Ta25 high-temperature shape memory alloys (HTSMAs) produced via a cold rolling process. The primary objective centers on characterizing the oxidation kinetics, oxide scale morphology, and phase transformations induced by high-temperature air exposure, thereby elucidating the degradation mechanisms responsible for functional loss. The novelty of this study lies in its detailed thermogravimetric and microstructural analysis of Ti–Ta25 HTSMAs subjected to oxidation up to 1000 °C, revealing the formation of dual-oxide layers (TiO₂ and Ta₂O₅) and the suppression of the martensitic phase transformation due to oxygen-induced stabilization of α and ω phases. Unlike prior works focusing on Ti–Ta alloys with higher tantalum

content or limited thermal exposure, this work provides critical insights into the compositional sensitivity and thermal stability of Ti–Ta25 alloys, highlighting their transformation behavior under oxidation and identifying the thresholds beyond which functional degradation becomes irreversible. The study contributes to the advancement of HTSMA materials for elevated temperature applications by clarifying the interplay between oxidation mechanisms and transformation characteristics, thereby informing future alloy design and thermal protection strategies.

2 MATERIALS PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

50g Ti-Ta25 (at.%) HTSMA was melted using the vacuum argon arc–re–melting technique (Edmund Buhler GmbH Germany Arc-Melter equipment). Twelve–melting was made to get high homogeneity in the chemical composition of the resulting alloys. The ingots were homogenized at 1100°C for 25h in a vacuum and then quenched in cold water. After homogenization treatment, the ingots were cold-rolled into sheets with a thickness of 2mm. The cold rolling process was completed in two steps with an intermediate annealing treatment between each two rolling steps at 800 °C for 10 min. For more information about the preparation, method, and mechanical treatment (Khulief, 2020; Khulief & Dakhal, 2020; Maier et al., 2017). X-ray diffraction (XRD) studied the phases present prior to oxidation. The microstructures prior to oxidation tests were investigated using (OM), (SEM) and (TEM). The TEM foils were prepared using (FIB). Before and after the oxidation tests, phase transformation temperatures were studied using combined DTA / TGA using TA Instruments / SDT Q600. The DTA tests were performed at a temperature range of 20 to 1000°C at a rate of 20 °C.min⁻¹ under an argon-shielding atmosphere. The oxidation tests were performed using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and a Pyris1 PerkinElmer Thermo–gravimetric Analyser. The oxidation tests were studied in the temperature interval between 26°C and 1000°C at a rate 5°C.min⁻¹ in air. The air flux used for the oxidation tests was 20ml. min⁻¹. The microstructure changes and transformation temperatures induced by oxidation tests were investigated using TEM, FIB, and DTA / TGA.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Phase Characterization and Microstructure

The X RD data of the Ti – Ta25 HTSMA is presented in Fig. 1. As observed from the patterns, Ti

– Ta25 HTSMAs have two phases. The analysis of the diffraction pattern confirms the presence of β – phase with BCC structure. They reported that β – phase has been shown a martensitic transformation (Rynko et al., 2015) [2-6]. In addition, there are small peaks of α'' - phase observed from the XRD pattern. The predominance of the Ti – Ta25 HTSMA peaks in the X-ray diffraction analysed is in agreement with OM, SEM, and TEM results presented in Figs. 2, 3, and 4.

Optical micrographs of Ti – Ta25 HTSMA are presented in Fig. 2. The Ti – Ta25 HTSMA shows a homogeneous microstructure characterized by β – phase with typical equiaxed grains and α'' - phase martensitic with needle and plate-like grains. The martensite structure observed in Fig. 2 is similar to that in Ti – Ta HTSMAs reported in the work by (Khulief, 2020; Zhang et al., 2014). The SEM images of Ti – Ta25 HTSMAs are depicted in Fig. 3. The SEM micrographs of Ti – Ta25 HTSMAs show structural features that entirely conform with the results of those of the optical micrographs of the Ti – Ta25 HTSMA Fig. 2. It is observed from Fig. 3 that the Ti – Ta25 HTSMA microstructure consists of a predominantly typical equiaxed grain-phase structure (large grain size) and needle-like of α'' - phase.

The transmission electron microscopy results in Fig. 4 show that the Ti – Ta25 HTSMA consists of two phases, β -phase and α'' - phase, which were certified by selected area diffraction SAD pattern Fig. 4 (b, c). The electron diffraction pattern shows that the Ti Ta25 HTSMA consists of the β -phase and α'' - phase. The TEM analysis showed that the α'' - martensite phase is formed in Ti-Ta25 HTSMAs in line with the results from the DTA chart shown in

Fig. 1. OM Image of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA

Fig. 2. SEM Image of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA.

3.2 Thermo-gravimetric Analysis

The DTA data of the Ti - Ta25 HTSMAs' shown in Fig. 5. The phase transformation temperature for the heating peak is in good agreement with what was reported before in the literature (Maier et al., 2017). They re-ported that the transformation temperature for Ti – Ta25 HTSMA is 350 °C, while in our study, the transformation is about 342 °C. However, it is noticeable that another trans-formation occurs at a peak around 515 °C. It was reported that the additional peak could be related to the first cycle effect (Buenconsejo, Kim, Hosoda, et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2011). However, our study might be related to the microstructural stability. It was reported be-fore that the beta-phase is a metastable phase in the range of temperature 250 °C - 600 °C (Cahn, 1991). They reported that the omega-phase could form from 100 °C to 400 °C (Cahn, 1991; Hickman, 1969; Niendorf et al., 2015). Furthermore, alpha-phase can form at temperatures higher than 400°C (Cahn, 1991; Gray III et al., 1992; Williams et al., 1971). The result of the additional peak during heat-ing in the present study fits with those reported by (Maier et al., 2017). Also, the phase trans-formation in the Ti –Ta25

Fig. 5

Fig. 1. XRD profiles of Ti - Ta25 HTSMAs.

HTSMAs in the present study occurs at $A_s = 342^\circ\text{C}$, $A_f = 437^\circ\text{C}$, higher than those reported in (Maier et al., 2017).

Fig. 3. TEM analysis of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA

The dynamic curve of Ti-Ta25 HTSMA oxidized at room temperature in air up to 1000°C is presented in Fig. 6. The results revealed that Ti-Ta25 HTSMA's oxidation behavior following a varied bath depends on the temperature evolution. According to the graph in Fig. 6, the mass loss was observed at the beginning, indicating the evaporation of solvents, which were used before the oxidation test during ultrasonic cleaning in the alloy preparation steps. Furthermore, it can be attributed to oxide scale spallation. These results agree with what was reported in (Khulief & Mahdy, 2022).

Based on the observation from Fig. 6, the oxidation behavior can be divided into three stages: initial stage, steady state, and parabolic stage. During the initial stage, $50^\circ\text{C} - 250^\circ\text{C}$, first until 100°C , the oxidation rate is very slow, and no sign of mass gain can be observed. Then, from $100^\circ\text{C} - 250^\circ\text{C}$, the oxidation rate increased by increasing the temperature, and a skinny oxide scale formed on the surface of Ti-Ta25 HTSMAs. During the second stage, $250^\circ\text{C} - 600^\circ\text{C}$, a linear mass gain was observed with a slight specific weight gain, which indicates that the oxidation of Ti-Ta25 HTSMA at range temperatures $250^\circ\text{C} - 600^\circ\text{C}$ not significant. This result is in line with the data from (Khulief & Mahdy, 2022). They reported that the steady state of Ti-Ta30 and Ti-Ta20-Al5 HTSMAs start from 250°C to 650°C . During the third stage, a rapid weight gain was observed from 600°C until 1000°C , following a parabolic rate, which indicates that the oxidation rate is high during this stage and the mass gain increases very fast from 600°C until 1000°C . Thus, suggests that the oxidation initiation

temperature for Ti-Ta25 HTSMA is more than 600°C . During this stage, a thick oxide scale forms on the outer layer of Ti-Ta25 HTSMA.

The above result shows that the oxidation of Ti-Ta25 HTSMA at high temperatures above 700°C is determined by oxygen diffusion, leading to an increase in the mass gain rate. At temperatures above 700°C , the oxygen diffusion into the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA is higher than at temperatures below 700°C . Meanwhile, the oxidation of Ti-Ta25 at a

temperature range of 600°C to 700°C is governed by the movement of the metal cations to the metal oxide interface, and this shows that the thickness of the oxide scale plays a role in the oxidation rate and mass gain at temperatures range of 600°C to 700°C .

Fig. 4. DTA Chart of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetric Chart of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA

3.3 Influence of oxidation and transformation temperature

In order to study the microstructure of Ti-Ta25 HTSMA after oxidation and to identify the oxide. FIB was used for ion contrast images and for preparing TEM samples. The TEM samples have been prepared from the outer layer and the base alloy. The ion contrast image of Ti-Ta25 HTSMA after oxidation is presented in Fig. 7. Beneath a carbon protection layer, which was used during the focused ion beam process, (a thin or thick) oxide film is observed. The oxide scale is followed by a porous

mixed layer structure of two oxides. The two oxides identified by TEM results are TiO₂ and Ta₂O₅, as can be seen in Fig. 7- b. By diffraction, a layer of oxide was selected over the mix identified as TiO₂ and Ta₂O₅.

Furthermore, the selected area diffraction for the base alloy (Fig. 7- c) revealed the presence of Ti-rich phase precipitates as α - phase. Moreover, Ta - rich β - phase is clearly identified with BCC as a matrix. The selected area diffraction also illustrated the presence of the ω - phase. It was reported that for Ti - Ta HTSMAs at a concentration of 30% Ta and these temperatures (850 °C - 1000 °C), the microstructure should consist of only β - phase with BCC. However, the Ti-rich α - phase formation can be explained based on the oxygen diffusion leading to stabilization of the α - phase. In addition, there is a difference in Ta concentration in this alloy. Hence, the less the Ta concentration, the more probable the Ti-rich α - phase formation. The absence of martensite in the microstructure after oxidation is also confirmed by DTA analysis. The results do not show any martensitic transformation after oxidation, as shown in Fig. (8). The results show flat heat flow curves after oxidation.

Fig. 7. a) FIP analysis of Ti - Ta25 HTSMAs after oxidation, and TEM analysis of b) oxide, c) alloy

Fig. 8. DTA Chart of the Ti-Ta25 HTSMA after oxidation

4 CONCLUSIONS

1. Before oxidation, Ti-Ta25 HTSMA consisted of a beta phase and a martensite phase (β and α phases). After oxidation, the alloy consisted of beta, alpha, and omega phases ($\beta + \alpha + \omega$ phases).

2. Before oxidation, Ti-Ta25 HTSMA showed an austenitic transformation, with a start temperature of 342°C and a final transformation temperature of 437°C ($A_s = 342^\circ\text{C}$, $A_f = 437^\circ\text{C}$). After oxidation, the alloy did not show any transformation.

3. After air oxidation, the presence of oxygen leads to the formation of the Ti-rich α - phase; the oxygen leads to stabilizing the α - phase in Ti-Ta25 HTSMA.

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